

TU Delft Software Carpentry Workshop

Helper Information Sheet

Thank you for being a helper during our Software Carpentry Workshop (SCW)! As a helper you will either be a **Troubleshooter** and help learners out during the workshop with any setup problems or questions that they have (or anywhere else that they get stuck) or you will be a **Code Documenter**, closely documenting the commands/code used by the instructor so that the learners have something to fall back on.

As a helper, the idea is not that you know the lesson materials by heart, or that you're an expert in everything that is being taught. It is more important that you are comfortable with answering any questions participants have (**Troubleshooter**) or able to type along with the instructor (**Code Documenter**). You do not need to know all the answers: there will be other helpers that can help out if you are unable to answer a question. As a helper you're also there to learn from the questions of the learners and the experiences of other helpers/instructors!

Troubleshooter

Physical workshop

- Monitor the room for anyone that needs help (anyone that has a red sticky note up or is indicating that they need help in other ways).
- Monitor the collaborative document for questions and answer them or ask the instructor to answer them (remind them during a break for example).

Online workshop

- Monitor the Zoom chat for questions (either asked in general chat, or directed to you privately). Use @asker to clarify whose question you are answering.
 - If the issue can't be solved through the chat, ask the participant to post a screenshot in the google doc or ask for a breakout room.
 - You can ask for a breakout room in the Zoom chat or in the Slack channel.
- Be online on Slack for communication between the helpers/instructors and for any issues that arise that need to be solved outside of the Zoom chat.
 - If there are any problems with screen sharing in the breakout room, ask the facilitator to fix the issue in the Slack channel.
- Help learners out with exercises in breakout rooms (if these are scheduled in the programme)
 - During exercises in the breakout rooms the general lesson stops and you'll guide the participants through an exercise or discussion that the teacher has set up before the workshop.
 - Each breakout room has 1 Helper with 4-6 participants.
 - Participants are assigned per OS or grouped based on their Faculty or a common interest (whenever possible).

- Each breakout room will have a timer (right top corner) to indicate how much time you have to get through the exercise. Additional broadcast messages may be sent to let you know how much time you still have.
- Your main task in the breakout room is to encourage people to understand the exercise, interact with each other and work together on this. Every learner should be able to participate!
 - You can ask people to very briefly introduce themselves or start a conversation on your breakout grouping as a small icebreaker. It may be easier for people to speak up once they have already taken the hurdle of speaking in the first place.
 - You can encourage participants to turn their cameras on. Do not force them to do so: participation in the chat and/or speaking is equally valid.
 - In the breakout room you will see the chat option to talk to 'Everyone': this is only everyone that is in your breakout room (so this message will not appear to the other breakout rooms of the main rooms!)
 - If you need any additional help you can call out for help in the Slack channel.
 - Keep an eye on the time and ensure all parts of the exercise are covered.
 - If any discussions go off topic, try to get back on topic by offering to look up the answer later or to discuss this during the next break.
 - Some things you can try in the exercise breakout room:
 - Ask one of the learners to share their screen and let the rest of the room guide them through the exercise
 - If another participant gets stuck during the exercise, it might be needed that they share their screen instead.
 - If no one is willing to share their screen, you can also share your own screen and let the learners guide you through it.
 - Alternatively, you can ask everyone to go through the exercise themselves and encourage asking questions when they are stuck with anything.
- The learners will be asked about their Operating System (OS) in the first icebreaker on Day 1: do check that information whenever you need it!

Code Documenter

- One of the helpers will be responsible for documenting the commands/code used during the session, with another helper as back up in case the code documenter needs a break.
- As the Code Documenter you do *not* need to help out participants with their questions as you will be too busy trying to follow the instructor's moves.
 - In a physical setting you can sit in the back or on the side of the room and ignore the post-its from the learners.
 - In an online workshop you do not have to lead breakout rooms, help

participants in breakout rooms, or keep an eye on the chat.

- There will be a separate section for the code documenting in the collaborative notes.
- The code documenter should ensure that the live coding is captured as well as possible: the commands used and if possible an explanation of the commands or script (through comments #).
- You can type along with the live coding, copy paste the code from the Carpentries materials if these are followed strictly, or take screenshots (if online - worked well for the Jupyter Notebook part).
- For online note taking only: The Zoom DJ will sometimes break into your note taking to add when people that need help are in breakout rooms. This way, these learners can go back to the document to see what they have missed when they were outside of the main session. You will notice by *** [name] is in breakout room *** etc. Please do not move these messages to ensure that the learner does not miss anything from the main session.

Checklist before the workshop

All helpers (Troubleshooters + Code documenters)

- Review the curriculum the instructors will be teaching (see the Carpentries website, or the workshop website).
- Make sure you are listed on the workshop website to receive official credit for helping.
- Did you join the Slack Channel? (email the coordinator for an up to date link) (*online*)
- Is your microphone/camera working properly? (*online*)
- Enter the Zoom-room a bit before the workshop starts to get settled, introduce yourself to other helpers, and add (Helper) in front of your name.
 - You can rename yourself in Zoom using the options button that has three dots on it and is situated in the top right corner of your Zoom portrait.

Troubleshooters

- Review the software installation instructions to be prepared to troubleshoot with learners. Please see this [overview for some of the expected issues and their solutions](#).
- Review the [teaching rules below](#) (page 5).
- Review if you need to prepare to lead any exercises in breakout rooms (see the coordination programme) (*online*)
- During the workshop: If there are breakout rooms that you're leading, have you been made a co-host or are you able to move to breakout rooms yourself? (*online*)

Code documenters

- Review the documented code in the collaborative docs from previous workshops if it is your first time as a code documenter to familiarise yourself with the process ([Code documenter](#))

After the workshop

- Provide feedback to the instructors and the team to improve future workshops/teaching.

Once you have helped during a workshop you can also consider [becoming a Carpentries Instructor](#) yourself!

Additional information

- [Software Carpentries helper checklist](#)
- [Why be a helper at Software Carpentry workshops?](#)
- [The Carpentries: How We Operate](#)

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Teaching Rules from The Carpentries Handbook

Rule #1: Be kind

This means to be inclusive, respectful, mindful and welcoming.

Rule #2: Remember that we are all learners

Admitting that you do not know everything helps create a growth mindset, where we are all constantly learning. When you make a mistake, calmly talk about the error, how it is part of the process and necessary to make progress.

Rule #3: Be aware of demotivating attitudes

There are several things that can be demotivating or impair the learners' experience. Examples of what not to do:

- Take over the learner's keyboard. Instead, encourage and guide them through the solution, but let them type themselves.
- Dive into deep discussions with more advanced learners (who might actually not need to be there). You can have those conversations during the break.

Rule #4: Be aware of demotivating words

Avoid saying things like:

- Just: "oh, that is easy, you just..."
- "It is too easy..." or "It is too hard..."
- "I cannot believe you do not know X ..."
- Say negative things about any applications or OS (Word, Excel, Windows, Mac, GUI). No tool is perfect, and this kind of disdain is not productive or conducive to the learning process.